

EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND TOOLS IN THE LESSON

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The effectiveness of teaching methods and tools is an important aspect of education because it directly affects student learning outcomes. A variety of approaches and resources are used in classrooms to engage students and facilitate effective learning experiences. The main points regarding the effectiveness of educational methods and tools are as follows:

1. Active learning. Learning methods that involve active student participation, such as roundtable discussions, group work, experiments, and hands-on activities, are more effective than traditional, passive learning methods. Active learning promotes student engagement, critical thinking, and knowledge retention.

2. Technology integration. Integrating technology tools such as interactive whiteboards, educational apps, online resources, and multimedia presentations has the potential to further enhance learning and teaching. Technology provides supplemental materials, fosters creativity, enables personalized learning, and facilitates easier access to information.

3. Differentiated Instruction: Adapting teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students is essential. Differentiated instruction involves tailoring content, tasks, and instructional strategies to accommodate individual learning styles, abilities, and interests. This personal approach supports student engagement, motivation and achievement.

4. Formative Assessment: Regularly assess student learning through formative assessment methods such as quizzes, class discussions, projects, and self-reflection activities to determine understanding and provide timely feedback to teachers. Formative assessment supports student learning, identifies areas for improvement, and informs instructional and pedagogical adjustments.

5. Cooperative Learning: Encouraging cooperation and teamwork among students through cooperative learning methods leads to improved learning outcomes. Collaborative activities promote communication, problem-solving skills, and social interaction, contributing to a positive classroom environment.

6. Visual Aids: Using visual aids such as diagrams, charts, graphic organizers can facilitate understanding and knowledge retention. Visual representations help students organize information, make connections, and strengthen understanding.

7. Provide active feedback: Providing constructive feedback helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Effective feedback should be clear, timely, and effective. Encourages students to reflect, revise, and grow on their learning journey.

It should be noted that the effectiveness of educational methods and tools may vary depending on the concept, subject matter and demographic indicators of students. Teachers must consider the unique needs of their students and continually evaluate and adapt instructional practices to ensure effective learning experiences.

The success of the educational process depends not only on its form, but also on the effectiveness of the methods and tools used, which occupies one of the main places in the theory of education. "Method" comes from the Greek word "methodos" - "way", which means research. The educational method is a joint activity aimed at achieving a specific goal of the teacher and students in the educational process. Educational methods mean the methods of achieving the goals of teaching and the ways of theoretical and practical orientation of the educational material. Teaching methods determine how the activity of the teacher and the learner should be in the educational process, how the educational process should be organized and conducted, and what activities the learners should perform in this process. Also, the educational method is the way of theoretical and practical cognitive activities aimed at the fulfillment of the educational tasks of teachers and learners. Educational methods depend on understanding the general laws of knowledge of the surrounding world, that is, they have a philosophical methodological basis and are the result of a correct understanding of the contradictions in the educational process, the essence and principles of the educational process. Educational material depends on the logic of scientific thought expressed in educational content. The less the theory is expressed in pedagogical views, the less the educational methods depend on this theory. The science of pedagogy summarizes the best practices of schools and educators, shows the scientific basis of traditional education, and helps to creatively search for modern, effective methods of teaching.

For this reason, the following basic requirements are set for educational methods:

1. The way of studying the educational material should lead to the formation of didactic-materialistic methods of thinking, the willful qualities of morality and behavior based on national ideology and national values.

2. The educational method should be clearly and clearly based on scientific evidence.

3. The systematicity of educational methods determines their level of effectiveness.

4. Another requirement that is inevitably placed on educational methods is their comprehensibility.

5. To teach the child to know through the senses and to use instructional tools as much as possible in the educational process.

6. Another requirement for educational methods is that the knowledge is reasonable and thorough. Educational methods should be effective.

The teacher's explanation and the learner's learning method must produce the planned or intended result. In the science of pedagogy, on the basis of learning and summarizing the practical experience of teachers, certain approaches are created depending on the conditions and specific circumstances of the educational process. When choosing educational methods, the following circumstances should be taken into account: General goals of education. The content and peculiarities of science and the subject being studied. Peculiarities of the methodology of teaching a subject. Time spent studying the material. Purpose, tasks and content of training. Age and cognitive abilities of students. Level of preparation of students. Financial support of the educational institution. Theoretical, practical and methodical preparation of the teacher, level of mastery of pedagogical skills. Educational methods are used together with educational tools. Educational tools are objects used by teachers and students to acquire new knowledge. Educational tools are of great importance in pedagogy. All means of education successfully implement educational goals. Educational tools reflect the material or spiritual values necessary to achieve educational goals. Usually, they are used in accordance with educational methods. But if the methods are "how to teach?" answers the question, and the tools "what to teach with it?" answers the question.

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